

Polarographic Investigations on In(III) Complexes

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In(III) has been found to be irreversibly reduced polarographically in alkaline medium in the presence of triethanolamine. The kinetic parameters of the process have been calculated.

THE polarographic reduction of In(III) has been studied mostly in acid solutions¹⁻⁸. Fewer studies have been made in alkaline medium. It has been mentioned⁹ that the half-wave potential of In(III) is $-1.13V$ vs. S.C.E. in $1N$ NaOH solution. The hydrolysis of dilute alkaline solution of In(III) with the consequent precipitation of indium hydroxide imposes limitation on such studies. In solution of higher alkali concentration precipitation of indium hydroxide is prevented due to the formation of alkali indates. It has been observed by the present investigators that the $E_{1/2}$ value of such solution becomes more negative indicating stabler species in solution. Thus the $E_{1/2}$ value of $10^{-3}M$ In(III) in $15M$ NaOH is $-1.38V$ vs. S.C.E. However, in the presence of triethanolamine the hydrolytic tendency of In(III) is inhibited in weakly alkaline solution. The present communication deals with the polarographic reduction of stabilised solution of In(III) in the presence of triethanolamine at a low NaOH concentration. The presence of more than one co-ordinated species in solution is indicated. The kinetic parameters of the irreversible electrode process have been calculated.

Reagents :

Indium perchlorate (prepared by dissolving freshly prepared indium hydroxide in pure perchloric acid and crystallisation) was dissolved in water and standardised by usual gravimetric procedure. A solution of gelatine was freshly prepared every time it was used. All the other chemicals were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. The composition of the solution was obtained by mixing In(III) perchlorate, sodium perchlorate, variable amounts of sodium hydroxide and triethanolamine—the ingredients being so chosen that the total ionic strength was kept constant ($\mu = 1$).

Preparation of solution :

Requisite quantity of NaOH was dissolved in water, to which required quantity of triethanolamine was added. The solution was cooled to 5° , and required volume of In(III) perchlorate solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solution was preserved in the cold to avoid any hydrolytic

Fig. 1

decomposition. A typical polarogram obtained from such a solution with $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.05M$ triethanolamine and $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) is shown in Fig. 1. The plot of E.d.e. vs. $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ is found to be linear.

Apparatus :

A Cambridge pen-recording polarograph was used for the measurement of the current voltage curves. The characteristics of the capillary used was $m = 1.61$ mg/sec, $t = 2.679$ sec ($m =$ flow rate of Hg and $t =$ drop time) in a solution to be examined at $-1.5V$ vs. S.C.E. at a height of 60 cm of the mercury reservoir. The sample solution was connected to the saturated calomel electrode through the bridges of agar-sodium perchlorate ($2M$), a sodium perchlorate solution ($2M$) and an agar-sodium perchlorate. Total resistance of the cell was found to be negligible and it did not change noticeably as the composition of the mixture was varied and so it was neglected in measuring the half-wave potential. All the polarographic measurements were made at $25^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ unless otherwise stated. Electrolytic hydrogen gas was used for removing oxygen from the solutions before polarograms were obtained.

Results and Discussion

The effect of mercury height :

At eight various applied heights of the mercury column (60, 55, 50, 45, 40, 35, 30 and 27.5 cm), the value of i_d/h^2 corrected (h corrected = effective height of Hg) was found to be $0.754 \pm 0.016 \mu$ amp/cm² for a solution of $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.3M$ triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine. The half wave potentials were constant within $\pm 0.01V$. The limiting current thus appeared to be due to a diffusion controlled process.

Effect of temperature :

From the study of a solution of $10^{-3}M$ In(III) in $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.1M$ triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine, the half-wave potential ($-1.360V$ vs. S.C.E.) did not change at first with an increase in the temperature (upto 20°) but it changed to more positive value as the temperature was further increased ($-1.263V$ vs. S.C.E. at 50°). A plot of half-wave potential vs. temperature was found to be horizontal upto a temperature of 20° and then fell linearly at higher ones (Fig. 2). Plot of $\ln i_d$ vs. $1/T$ ($i_d =$ diffusion current and $T =$ temperature in absolute scale) gave a straight line from the slope of which the activation energy of diffusion was calculated to be 1.537 Kcal. This result also indicates that the limiting current was diffusion controlled.

The values of αn , k^0_f and D , calculated at different temperatures for a solution of $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.1M$ triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) in the presence of 0.005 per cent gelatine are tabulated below :

Diffusion coefficient values were obtained by using the Ilkovic's equation,

Fig- 2

TABLE

Temp. °K	$E_{1/2(N.H.E.)}$ in Volts	αn	* D (cm ² /sec)	k^0_f (cm/sec)
283	-1.1185	0.4375	1.597×10^{-4}	6.310×10^{-12}
288	-1.1185	0.4741	1.760×10^{-4}	9.333×10^{-12}
293	-1.1185	0.4648	1.932×10^{-4}	1.413×10^{-11}
298	-1.092	0.4298	3.783×10^{-4}	6.252×10^{-9}
303	-1.0825	0.3654	4.006×10^{-4}	9.247×10^{-9}
308	-1.0810	0.3338	4.592×10^{-4}	1.276×10^{-8}
313	-1.0660	0.3260	4.840×10^{-4}	1.982×10^{-8}
318	-1.0550	0.3100	5.217×10^{-4}	2.924×10^{-8}
323	-1.0215	0.2920	5.608×10^{-4}	5.546×10^{-8}

* Calculated from the average value of αn .

$$D^{\ddagger} = i_d/607 ncm^{2/3}t^{1/6}$$

'n' in the equation being substituted by ' αn '.

The rate constant, k^0_f , referred to $0.0V$ vs. N.H.E. was evaluated from the equation¹⁰,

$$E_{1/2(Nf.H.E.)} = \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} [2.3 \log (k^0_f f^0 . D^{-1}) + 1.15 \log t - 0.12]$$

From the plot of $\log k^0_f$ against $1/T$, two different values for the apparent activation energy (Q) were obtained (14.65 and 13.24 KCal) which indicated the different reaction mechanisms with change of temperature which is also indicated by the plot of half-wave potential against temperature (Fig. 2). It may be mentioned that variation of In(III) ion concentration from $0.1 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ in solutions having a constant amount of triethanolamine ($0.3M$)

did not affect the half-wave potential. This observation excludes the possibility of existence of polynuclear complexes.

Effect of change of concentration of triethanolamine :

From the study of a solution of $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.1M$ NaOH, varying concentrations of triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine, it was found that the half wave potential ($-1.36V$ vs. S.C.E.) did not change as the concentration of triethanolamine was changed from $0.03M$ to $0.1M$. The half wave potential changed to more negative values as the concentration of triethanolamine was further increased [$E_{1/2} = -1.50V$ vs. S.C.E. at $2M$ triethanolamine]. Upto $0.5M$ triethanolamine concentration, the diffusion current was constant but with further increase of triethanolamine concentration i_d value decreased. Plot of E.d.e. vs. $\log i_d - i$ was linear in all cases. From the plot of logarithm of triethanolamine concentration against $E_{1/2}$, it appeared that more than one type of complex were present in solution.

Effect of change of concentration of In(III) :

In solutions containing varied concentrations of In(III) [from $0.1 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $2 \times 10^{-3}M$], $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.3M$ triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ (to make $\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine, diffusion current (i_d) increased with the increase in In(III) concentration. The half-wave potential value was found to be constant at $-1.41 \pm 0.01V$. A plot of i_d vs. concentration of In(III) was linear upto the In(III) concentration of $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ and the value of the diffusion current constant was found to be 4.106 .

Effect of change of NaOH concentration :

From the study of $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.3M$ triethanolamine, varying concentrations of NaOH (from $0.1M$ to $1M$), $NaClO_4$ ($\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine, it was found that the half-wave potential changed slightly to more negative value with the increase in NaOH concentration.

Effect of solvent :

Some recent studies¹¹ in non-aqueous media indicate stepwise reduction of In(III) in complexes with ligands like tropolone, dithiol, oxine, acetylacetone and similar other bidentate chelating ligands. With triethanolamine, however, we failed to get more than one irreversible wave in methanol-water and acetonitrile solvents. A solution of $10^{-3}M$ In(III), $0.1M$ NaOH, $0.3M$ triethanolamine, $NaClO_4$ ($\mu = 1$) and 0.005% gelatine in 1 : 1 methanol : water gave a well defined wave with the half-wave potential of $-1.382V$ vs. S.C.E. In pure acetonitrile solvent, the half-wave potential value was found to be $-1.636V$ vs. S.C.E.

Further studies on the polarographic reduction of In(III) with the ethanolamines are in progress.

References

1. J. HEYROVSKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1925, **19**, 168.
2. S. TAKAGI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 301.
3. J. LINGANE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2099.
4. H. J. NAKATANI, *Sci. Hiroshima Univ.*, 1955, **19**, 183.
5. N. V. AKESLRUD, *Ukrain Zhur Khim*, 1955, **21**, 457.
6. S. INOUE and H. IMAI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1960, **33**, 149.
7. E. D. MOORHEAD and W. M. MACNEVIN, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 269.
8. J. A. SCHUFLE, M. F. STUBBS and R. WITMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1013.
9. J. HEYROVSKY and D. ILKOVIC, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1935, **7**, 198.
10. H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1955, **28**, 422.
11. D. G. TUCK and M. K. YANG, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1972, 3100 and *J. Chem. Soc., (A)*, 1971, 214.